

Update of the CHESTER Simulation Framework for Fission Chambers Simulation

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ABSTRACT

A complete reimplementa-tion of the CHESTER framework, originally developed in 2012 to simulate neutron-induced charge spectra and pulse shapes in fission chambers, is presented. The new version, CHESTER25, has been completely rewritten in C++ under Linux to ensure compatibility with the latest versions of Garfield++, MAGBOLTZ, SRIM, and ROOT. It retains the original computational approach while improving maintainability, modularity, and integration with modern simulation tools. New capabilities have been added, such as the addition of a magnetic field to the simulation and the ability to simulate chambers with plane-parallel electrodes such as COREX. Comparisons with original CHESTER and experimental data show consistent results, confirming the reliability of the updated framework for fission chamber modeling and nuclear instrumentation studies.

Keywords: Simulation, Fission Chamber, Instrumentation

1. INTRODUCTION

In the context of actual and future nuclear reactor developments, accurate neutron flux monitoring is mandatory to ensure reactor safety and optimizing reactor operation. Accurate neutron flux measurements are also essential for characterizing experimental conditions in research facilities such as the Jules Horowitz reactor (RJH) being built at CEA Cadarache. These systems require detectors capable of withstanding high levels of radiation while providing an accurate and on-line flux measurements. Among the detectors capable of providing reliable online flux measurements, fission chambers [1] stand out for their robustness, stability and ability to operate in extreme environments exposed to high neutron and γ -ray flux. The design and optimization of such detectors involve complex physical processes. It can be achieved by a combination of experimental feedback and simulating tools.

The Dosimetry, Sensors and Instrumentation Laboratory (LDCI) at CEA Cadarache has developed and maintained several simulation tools for nuclear instrumentation studies. One of these tools is CHESTER, a simulation framework initially developed in 2012 to model and predict the responses of fission chambers under different neutrons fluxes, gases, and electric field configuration [2]. The original version, CHESTER12, was successfully validated against experimental results from the FICTIONS-8 experiment undertaken at the BR2 reactor [3], demonstrating its ability to reproduce realistic fission chambers signals.

In recent years, however, major updates to the underlying simulation codes, such as Garfield ++ [4], MAGBOLTZ [5], and SRIM [6] have rendered the original version of CHESTER incompatible with current computing environments. The objective of this work is to restore and modernize the framework through a complete reimplementa-tion in C++, resulting in CHESTER25, while ensuring that it reproduces the same physical results as the original version.

In addition to restoring functionality, CHESTER25 introduces several new features, including a configuration file that simplifies user interaction, and the ability to simulate magnetic field effects and planar chamber geometries such as the COREX device, which will enable testing of future models and simulation codes [7]. This paper presents the integration of the modern software dependencies, the technical updates implemented as well as the new features and a comparison of the results obtained with CHESTER25 to those from CHESTER12 and the FICTIONS-8 experiment.

2. SIMULATION FRAMEWORK

CHESTER25 follows the same computational route as the original CHESTER12 framework, developed to simulate the full signal formation process in fission chambers. The framework models all stages from the generation of fission fragments to the induced current on the electrodes, assuming independent ionization processes, negligible recombination and space charge effects.

The simulation relies on three main toolkits: Garfield++, MAGBOLTZ and SRIM. Garfield++ is a C++ reimplementation of the original Fortran 77 Garfield code and provides the detector modeling environment. It integrates MAGBOLTZ, which solves the Boltzmann transport equation for electrons using Monte Carlo methods to obtain drift and diffusion coefficients. It interfaces with SRIM to compute the stopping power and the energy loss of fission fragments in the detector gas and fissile deposit.

The overall simulation sequence implemented in CHESTER25 is summarized in Table I. It includes gas and field definition, fission fragments tracking, charge pair generation and drift simulation, and induced signal calculation. The code simulates n fission products individually during the loop shown in Table I. Charge motion is computed using the Runge-Kutta-Fehlberg (RKF) method to integrate drift equations, while the induced current on the electrodes is obtained through the Shockley-Ramo theorem [8] [9].

Table I: Overview of the CHESTER25 simulation route.

Level	Function	Methods	Code/Tool
Program foundation	Interface, execution, configuration, file reading	—	Linux, C++, Cmake
ComponentAnalyticField	Electric field computation	Analytical or finite element	Garfield++
MediumMagboltz	-Gas definition (pressure, temperature, composition) -Electron transport coefficients	Boltzmann equation resolution by Monte Carlo method	MAGBOLTZ
TrackSrim & TrackTrim	-FF trajectories, energy loss -Charge pair creation	Semi empirical model	SRIM
DriftRKF	Charge pairs drift simulation	Runge-Kutta-Fehlberg	Garfield++
Sensor	Induced signal calculation	Shockley-Ramo theorem	Garfield++
Data Processing	Results display	—	ROOT, C++

This modular approach preserves the original physical modeling of CHESTER12 while enabling compatibility with modern C++ based computational environments. For detailed equations and theoretical background, readers are referred to Ref [2].

3. CHESTER25: Framework Modernization and New Features

3.1. Code Modernization and Reimplementation

The redevelopment of CHESTER was driven by the transition from the original Garfield code, written in Fortran 77, to its modern C++ reimplementation Garfield++. This major change required a complete redesign of the software architecture to ensure compatibility and long-term maintainability.

CHESTER25 has been entirely rewritten in C++ and organized into several independent modules. Each module handles a specific simulation task, such as geometry definition, electric field computation, charge drift, or signal reconstruction. This makes the framework more modular and easier to update.

A configuration file is now used to describe the characteristics of the fission chamber to be simulated. This file allows the physical simulation parameters to be described, such as geometry, gas composition, pressure, applied voltage, fissile deposit thickness, as well as simulation configuration parameters. This approach allows us to simulate different detectors without having to modify the code or recompile it, which greatly improves flexibility and ease of use. CHESTER25 was deliberately written as a clear, easily readable code to facilitate future maintenance. The code currently consists of around twenty functions and runs on Linux operating system. Linux was chosen to ensure good compatibility and ease of use, as C++, Garfield++, ROOT and other dependencies were originally designed for Linux.

Overall, CHESTER25 preserves the physical modeling approach of CHESTER12 while providing a clean, modular, and maintainable foundation for future developments and extensions of the fission chambers simulation framework.

3.2. Exploration of the TRIM algorithm

Until now, the simulation of fission product trajectories in gas has been performed using the SRIM algorithm, which provides rapid output in the form of a text file read by Garfield++. However, this method sometimes leads to unrealistic simulations of trajectories because the electrons are grouped together in clusters. Figure 1 shows a particular trajectory simulated by Garfield using a SRIM file, in which the fission product returns to the anode, which is physically impossible. Up to 50% of the fission products starting from one electrode return almost immediately to the same electrode, those events are clearly simulation artefacts and will not be considered in the future. More generally, the trajectory of a fission product is much straighter than that obtained with SRIM. However, the difference is compensated in mean but not in variance [2].

In order to investigate possible improvements, the use of TRIM (Transport of Ions in Matter) [10] trajectories was explored. Unlike SRIM tables, TRIM can generate complete spatial trajectories with detailed coordinates and energy loss information. These files can be imported into Garfield++ to simulate much more realistic fission product trajectories (right side of Figure 1) but this method is about ten times slower than the SRIM one. Another approach was tested, namely disabling straggling in the SRIM method.

Figure 2 shows the charge spectra of CHESTER25 using these three methods. The trajectories obtained with SRIM without straggling and TRIM generate up to 50% more charge leading to higher average pulses. The Garfield++ algorithm could promote charge creation in the case of a straight trajectory. A complete implementation of the TRIM method was not carried out due to these results being less close to physical reality than with the SRIM method.

It is still possible to use the TRIM method. To do so, the user must generate text files in Windows and integrate them into CHESTER25 in Linux. This procedure is significantly longer and more complex.

3.3. Magnetic Field Simulation Capability

CHESTER25 is now capable of simulating the effects of a magnetic field on a fission chamber, which will help in the development of instrumentation of fusion tokamaks such as ITER or DEMO. The

Figure 1: A failed SRIM simulation (left) where the fission product (green line) returns to the anode. And a TRIM simulation (right). The red lines represent the drift of electrons and the yellow lines represent ions.

magnetic field parameters can be defined directly in the configuration file, provided that the corresponding gas file, containing the magnetic field data, has been generated beforehand using MAGBOLTZ. The calculation steps remain identical to those for the case without a magnetic field, with the exception of a few adjustments. The presence of a magnetic field breaks the cylindrical symmetry of the system, except when it is oriented along the chamber axis. An azimuthal angle θ is randomly selected for each event, and for a deposit located on the anode, the starting point of the fission product is defined by the coordinates $(r_a \cos \theta, r_a \sin \theta, z)$. Given its kinetic energy, the fission product is not deflected by the magnetic field. However, as shown in Figure 3, electrons are subject to the Lorentz force and their trajectory is visibly deflected, unlike that of heavier ions. With a magnetic field of 10 T oriented along the chamber axis and a reduced electric field of approximately 8 Td, this results in a 10% longer electronic pulse duration (Figure 4), which correspond to the deviation of their trajectory.

Figure 2: Comparison of charge spectra for SRIM, SRIM without straggling, and TRIM methods (left) and comparison of average pulses for the same three methods (right).

3.4. Extended Geometry Support

The CHESTER simulation code is now also capable of simulating chambers with parallel plane geometry such as a CFTM and, in particular, the COREX device [7]. COREX is a modular device consisting of two parallel planar electrodes, separated by a Frisch grid, with a uranium-233 deposit on the cathode, emitting α particles at 4.824 MeV and 4.784 MeV (Figure 5). The Frisch grid isolates the anode from the direct induction of electrons generated in the ionization region. This device was designed to explore the physics of fission chambers, in particular the Boag-Chabod columnar

Figure 3: In green, the trajectory of the fission product, in orange the path of the electrons, and in red the argon ions with a magnetic field.

Figure 4: Average pulses from a CFUR under the influence of various magnetic fields.

recombination model [11], [12], using the Frisch grid [13] technique to measure the angle of incidence of the alpha particle [14].

The implementation of COREX geometry in CHESTER allows simulations to be performed under various gas mixtures and pressures, providing a framework for studying charge transport phenomena in fission chambers. In the future, adding a columnar recombination model to CHESTER would enable more accurate simulation results to be obtained and would also allow the RCBC model to be tested through simulation. Figure 6 shows an example of simulated charge induced on the anode, cathode, and Frisch grid as a function of time, illustrating the respective contributions of the signals and the effect of grid inefficiency.

Figure 5: Diagram of the COREX device

Figure 6: Computed charge induced over time on the three electrodes by a 4.8 MeV alpha particle in pure argon at 4 bar with a voltage of 2000 V on the anode, -10 V on the grid, and -2000 V on the cathode.

4. Validation of CHESTER25 against CHESTER12 and FICTIONS-8

4.1. Simulation Setup and Test Cases

CHESTER25 simulations were performed on the same five fission chambers with cylindrical geometry tested in CHESTER12, their characteristics are detailed in Table II.

Table II : Input data for the fission chambers

	CFUZ	CFUR	CF4	CF8	CFUM11
r_a (mm)	0.35	1	1.25	0.5	10
r_c (mm)	0.65	1.25	1.75	3.15	12
Voltage	150	250	300	300	600
Longueur	47	14	12	33.5	227
Gaz	Ar+4%N ₂	Ar+4%N ₂	Ar	Ar	Ar
Pression	5	5	12	9	4

4.2. Charge Spectra and Collection

The charge spectrum for the CFUZ and the CF8 are shown in Figure 7. For small fission chamber like the CFUZ, fission product deposit only partial energy, yielding single peaked spectra at ~440,000 electrons charges. Larger chamber like the CF8 exhibits characteristic dual peaks corresponding to heavy (~70 MeV) and light (~100 MeV) fission products. CHESTER25 results agree within 7% of experimental FICTIONS-8 data and CHESTER12 simulations (Table III).

Table III: Average charge spectra (in million charge units) for several CFs, comparison of Chester12, Chester25, and FICTIONS-8 data.

Average Charge	CFUR	CFUZ	CF4	CF8
CHESTER12	0.40	0.40	1.69	2.72
CHESTER25	0.39	0.43	1.71	2.84
FICTIONS-8	0.44	—	1.4	—

4.3. Mean Pulse Formation

The results obtained with CHESTER25 show excellent agreement with those obtained with CHESTER12. As summarized in Table IV for all the tested fission chambers.

Table IV: Average pulse duration and amplitude for several fission chambers, comparison of Chester12 and Chester25.

	Average pulse duration (2012)	Average pulse duration (2025)	Maximum average pulse amplitude (2012)	Maximum average pulse amplitude (2025)
CFUR	6.2 ns	6.2 ns	10 μ A	10.1 μ A
CFUZ	11.10 ns	11.25 ns	7.0 μ A	7.1 μ A
CF4	140 ns	144 ns	1.9 μ A	2.0 μ A
CF8	1300 ns	1350 ns	0.48 μ A	0.40 μ A

Figure 7: Charge spectrum for a CF4 (left) and CF8 (right).

5. Conclusion

The complete reimplementaion of the CHESTER framework has restored its functionality and ensured compatibility with modern computational tools. CHESTER25 reproduces the results obtained with CHESTER12 while maintaining consistency with FICTIONS-8 experimental campaign, confirming the validity of the original modeling approach and validating its reliability for fission chambers study. This new version provides a solid and maintainable basis for future developments. We have also extended its capacity by adding the possibility to simulate fission chambers in a magnetic field and planar geometry fission chambers or ionization chamber in the case of COREX. CHESTER could benefit from future experimental validation and the addition of a columnar recombination model to further strengthen its simulation capabilities.

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